

Quad2BIM

Good method statement for *Scan-to-HBIM* activities

To minimise risks in the workplace and maintain a high degree of health and safety for the personnel and public

A cooperative approach that brings completeness and inclusiveness
to the scan-to-BIM modeling process within the historical buildings life cycle

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<http://quad2bim.mfa.ulisboa.pt/>

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General information

Quad2BIM research project proposes a cooperative approach for HBIM in order to bring completeness and inclusiveness into the scan-to-BIM modeling process within the historic buildings life cycle. The proposed document has paramount importance for the research success and quality. It is applicable to the site and office activities implemented within *Quad2BIM* project and can be used as reference by all the professionals of the Scan-to-BIM field. It aims to establish, implement and maintain an OH&S management system to improve occupational health and safety, eliminate hazards and minimize OH&S risks (including system deficiencies), take advantage of OH&S opportunities, and address OH&S management system nonconformities associated with its activities.

This report is in compliance to the requirements of the NP ISO 45001:2019 standard (*Occupational health and safety management systems — Requirements with guidance for use*).

Project Name: _____

Project Number: _____

Site location: _____

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1. Introduction

This Method Statement sets out the safety management strategy adopted by the personnel during the course of Scan-to-HBIM operations for the *Quad2BIM* project, which include activities of surveying on site for the collection of the data and activities of postproduction in the office.

It can be applied to any other Scan-to-HBIM project (with due additions or omissions where necessary) as it provides the most common procedures that must be taken in order to ensure the health and safety of the public and the working team involved in the project.

The safety for the activities undertaken on the field are the focus of this document because they can expose the surveyors to potential dangers that can lead them to death. It also includes some common rules to prevent the spread of the current Covid-19 virus. It will offer some instruction for health and safety office-based activities as some details for the indoor conform.

Team members should read this document before the project starts. Project co-ordinator must confirm and verify all the information is correct during the first visit to the site.

2. Disclaimer

The details provided in this example method statement are intended as a guide only. The document is not intended to provide technical specifications. The hazards and control procedures listed may not be a comprehensive list as per the analysis, evaluation and mitigation solutions. You must ensure that the proposed document can provide an acceptable control for the significant hazards that will be present in your particular circumstance otherwise, you should integrate or amend it according to the local regulation. We cannot accept any responsibility for your subsequent acts or omissions. If you have any doubts, queries or concerns, you should refer to the relevant regulations and take further professional advice.

3. Safety policy

This Method Statement, in line with the European standards¹, aims to identify, analyse and mitigate the risks that surveyors and BIM technicians should be aware of as they represent the primary source of this research project and their health and safety is our greatest responsibility. The public shall be given equal priority to that of our team members. For this purpose, *Quad2BIM* operates in order to ensure that the following requirements are established:

- The provision and maintenance of any place and system of work are safe and without risks to health;
- Arrangements for ensuring safety and absence of risks to health in connection with the use, handling, storage and transport of the equipment;
- The provision of such information, instruction, training and supervision as is necessary to ensure the health and safety at work of the personnel;
- The provision and maintenance of a working environment for the personnel that is adequate as it regards the facilities and arrangements for their welfare at work².

Quad2BIM recognizes the risk management as a base for quality assurance and a sensitive field in which the communication management operates. For this reason, the success of health and safety management is dependent on the:

- Pro-active planning of all work activities;
- Level of competence of the personnel;
- Adequate risk assessment;
- Quality and efficiency of the communication between management and all employees.

¹ ISO 31000:2018 - Risk management – Guidelines; ISO/TR 31004:2013 - Risk management - Guidance for the implementation of ISO 31000; IEC 31010:2019 - Risk management - Risk assessment techniques; ISO 31022:2020 - Risk management - Guidelines for the management of legal risk; IWA 31:2020 - Risk management - Guidelines on using ISO 31000 in management systems; ISO 45001:2018 - Occupational health and safety management systems — Requirements with guidance for use

² Health and Safety at Work etc. Act 1974

All personnel reading this document should notify to the contracts manager if:

- They fail to understand any part of this Method Statement;
- They consider that any part of the document is incorrect or must be integrated;
- They consider that this document contrast with any contract information, scope of the job, technical specifications, standards or technical drawing;

4. Project information

In order accomplish the clients need and this research purpose, an accurate measured survey is require to document the current site and buildings arrangements, inform design and in support of any planning considerations. The location and extent of the measured survey has been highlighted on "Plan A" below:

Plan A: Scope of work

The work that comprises a land survey is to measure the required areas and features within a specific boundary or building and produce a twin model of the real world. The survey will be performed by a team of two or four surveyors. The 3D modelling by a sufficient number of technicians is needed to ensure the delivery of the project within the *Projected Completion Date* indicated in this document.

Project Start Date: _____

Expected Duration: _____

Projected Completion Date: _____

Project Manager: _____

Client contact number: _____ **Email** _____

Contact to call/email in case of emergency: _____

The method statement is to be reviewed by Operations Director. The Operations Director should incorporate any relevant comments and reviews into the document prior to the work commencing.

Review Record						
Edition/Version	Date	Status	Section	Page	Name	Signature
Issue A/ Rev 0	31/12/2020	Approved	all	all	Graziella Del Duca	<i>Graziella Del Duca</i>

Methods of Working

This section analyses and evaluates the working condition, in order to study the risk usually faced by the personnel during Scan-to-HBIM activities.

5. Equipment

Scan-to-HBIM process contemplates two phases: the first one, on site, aims to capture a high-density point cloud of a physical building, the second one leads to the creation of a as-built BIM model.

For the second phase BIM technicians only need a computer.

For the first phase, surveyors need one or more of the following sets of equipment in order to carry out the data collection:

1. Laser Scanner and Total Station kit
2. GPS kit
3. Drone kit
4. Disto and manual measuring instruments
5. Camera

6. Kit for 360° photos
7. Tripod
8. Tripod
9. Jack up tripod

6. Working days and hours

The work will be carried out from Monday to Friday, from 8.30 to 17.30. It maybe requested to start earlier or finish late.

7. Sequence of work for surveying

Preliminary actions

Before any site activities start:

- The client shall ensure that Quad2BIM team has the right to access the site for the duration of the project, during normal working hours, namely from 08.30 to 17.30 hours, for the purposes of carrying out the survey and the documentation needed
- The client shall ensure that the site is safe and shall comply with all national requirements as regards to the health and safety at work and any other relevant rules and regulations. In addition, the client shall inform Quad2BIM project coordinator of the site safety conditions in order to apply all health and safety rules, regulations and any other reasonable security requirements that apply to the site.

Manual Handling

All surveying equipment must be lifted safely and handled correctly.

- It is easier and safer to push than to pull.
- Surveyors should get help when needed.
- Surveyors should not lift or carry things they do not feel comfortable with, no matter how light the load and use mechanical assistance if required.

Survey control points

Once the site is safe to access and the data acquisition can start, a control network is defined by fix points on the ground. Surveyor shall measure those points by total station and GPS in order to relate the entire surveyed data to them. When possible, national geodetic marks are included into the survey and used as main reference.

- This operation usually needs a team of at least two people.

- The total station and the prisms must be set up safely on the tripods in order to avoid falls.
- Tripods must be stable and set up on dry and hard ground. A fix base, namely the "spider", can be used at the base of the legs to mitigate slipping of the tripod.
- Most of the activity for the acquisition of the survey control points is on the public pavements. Specific PPE³ are needed (HiVis Jacket and equipment to cordon off the working area).

Scanner Survey

The scanner survey is the largest activity on site.

For the Quad2BIM project, usually one or two people are required for this task according with the instruments availability.

Scans are taken approximately every 5m for internals 20m for externals.

The scan survey can be run in parallel with the acquirement of the survey control points, photo shooting and drone flight.

- The scanner is set up on a stable tripod as described per the measurement of the Survey control points.
- Roof data acquisition by laser scanning shall take into consideration the risk of operating at heights. The area must have a safe access, handrails or parapets over 0.95m
- Risk of injury is more probable if the building or part of it is derelict.
- Surveyors should avoid lone and night work.
- Only trained operators should make the measurement of confined spaces.

Jack Up tripod

Jack up tripod is often used to set the instruments at higher level in order to get more visibility and a wide range of points.

- Surveyor could need to use a ladder to set up the instrument and to use them.
- Possible risk of fall.

Data gathering by drone

Part of the external measured data (e.g the roof area) is collected by the postproduction of photographs taken by drone. The drone is also used for the internal where the access of some areas is limited or restricted.

- Only a trained pilot can flight the drone.
- It is suggested to pre-set the flight route previously in the office in order to optimize the time of usage of the drone on public spaces and reduce the risk of accidents.

Photos

Photos taken for a complete documentation of the current conditions of the building are used by the BIM technician for the visualization of the details of the site. For this reason a sufficient number of both site and 360° photos is needed.

- The risk connected with this activity is linked to the simultaneous operations of the surveyors and public within the site area and to the handling of tripods.

Contractors and visitors safety

Since Quad2BIM represents a research project of innovation, it can require the application or the testing of new instruments during the site activities. It may be happen that professionals, contractors and students are invited to visit the buildings.

- All the site areas must be left clear of the instruments and equipment at the end of each working day.

Office-based work

All the activities of pre-processing, processing of the measured data and the 3D modelling are implemented in the office.

- Office layout, workstations and equipment should allow the employees to move in the office without obstacles.
- Technicians should keep a good posture while working at the computer in order to avoid pain and damages to the spine, adjust the chair, desk, and screen height.

- Workers should change posture at frequent intervals to minimise fatigue and avoid awkward postures at the extremes of the joint range, especially the wrists. It is best to take frequent short breaks rather than infrequent longer ones.
- The level of the screen brightness and the lighting should be adjusted in the room for ensuring a visual comfort.
- The office should have an adequate system of natural or artificial ventilation and heating/cooling

COVID-19 virus

Employers have a duty to reduce workplace risk to the lowest reasonably practicable level by taking preventative measures.

- Provide cleaning and disinfection of exposed areas.
- Respect social distance when possible.
- Prohibit shared food and beverages among employees.
- Train all personnel on new protocols and frequently communicate safety guidelines.
- An individual who screens positive for COVID-19 symptoms must not be allowed to enter the office.
- Work remotely if needed.

Requirements

This section describes the basic requirements and equipment necessary to implement a safe Scan-to-BIM job.

8. Staff preparation and roles

All members of staff are experienced surveyors and BIM technicians with previous experience of this type of project. They will be given copies of risk assessments and method statements before the site induction is made by the project coordinator.

A project coordinator will be appointed to each new project that will be responsible for quality and safety. Apprentices and students will be supervised and are not allowed to carry out tasks for which they have not been trained.

The Project Co-ordinator is responsible for the checking and verification of all plant and equipment as safe for use.

The Operations Director reviews the method statement.

Personnel involved in the project will be listed in the next section dedicated to the Risk Assessment

9. Personal Protective Equipment - PPE

All site workers should wear, safety boots, high visibility vests and protective clothing at all times; other items of PPE such as hard hats, eye/hearing protection, safety harness, lanyard and gloves are available to be worn as necessary.

10. First Aid

The appointed person as first-aider should look after first-aid equipment, facilities and call the emergency services when required.

Aid kit must be taken also on site

Employers and their first-aiders should take account of the specific guidance on giving cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR) due to the COVID-19 virus circumstances.

11. Welfare facilities

The staff will use the welfare facilities available in the site area, if none are present, toilet facilities will be identified within walking distance.

12. Site access

The authorization for relevant facilities have been obtained, and are kept on file

Risk Assessment

The Quad2BIM safety risk assessment is an instrument used to identify and assess active and latent safety hazards for Scan-to-HBIM operation. This safety risk assessment includes actions for mitigating the predicted probability and severity of the consequences or outcomes of each operational risk.

13. Hazards identified

- Manual handling
- Working at heights
- Moving, storing and transporting belongings end equipment heavy instruments
- Working on the roof
- Public interaction
- Derelicted building
- Covid-19

14. Drugs and alcohol

The personnel that has consumed alcohol or under influence of drugs is not allowed to work.

15. Emergency procedures

In case of accident, the following procedures must be executed:

- Alert the office and Report the accident and the due detail to the project manager
- Call ambulance in case of emergency
- The accident will be investigated
- The surveyors/technicians should raise the alarm and make their way to the nearest evacuation point in case of fire.
- The local hospital address is listed in the Risk Assessment tab

16. Risk Assessment

Safety risk probability

The safety risk probability is defined as the likelihood that the hazard might occur.

All scenarios should be taken into consideration. The probability is categorized into criteria such as numbers. These numbers are assigned to each probability level. The following figure displays a five levels probability table.

Probability Levels

Factor N.	Levels	Description
5	Almost certain	A dangerous situation occurs frequently
4	Likely	A dangerous situation can occur several times during the study period
3	Possible	A dangerous situation may occur at least once due to damage
2	Unlikely	A dangerous situation can occur
1	Rare	A dangerous situation is not expected

Risk severity

The risk severity is defined as the extent of harm that might reasonably occur as an outcome of the identified safety hazard. The severity assessment can be based on injuries (persons) and/or damages (equipment and buildings, power lines, or the cost dimension). The values of the expected consequence does not change after the application of the mitigation actions.

Expected consequence

Factor N.	Injury Severity	Description
5	Deadly or catastrophic	One or more deads or losts.
4	Serious injury	Permanent Disability or Injury
3	Moderate injury	Temporary disability; require medical treatment
2	Minor injury	Small injuries that do not require hospitalization; only first aid
1	Irrelevant	No injury

RISK ASSESSMENT for Scan-to-BIM activities

Project Code and Name:
Complete site address:

Assessment carried out by:
Date:
RA checked on site by:

Closest hospital name:
Person to contact at the office:

Phone N.1
Phone N.2
Phone N.

1. On site activity

Hazards - Risks

At Risk

Matrix assessment of risk (Max 125)

Control

Scores after risk mitigation (Max 125)

Risk ID	Hazard	Risk	Matrix assessment of risk (Max 125)		TOTAL RISK	Control		Scores after risk mitigation (Max 125)	
			Probability (1-5, 1=Low, 5=High)	Consequence (P x C = R _{tot})		Probability (1-5, 1=Low, 5=High)	Consequence (P x C = R _{mit})	RISK INDEX	
1	Personal risks	1 Team work/ work in contact with public	5	5	25	5	5	1	5
2	Staff health, comfort and welfare	COVID-19: Virus contagion COVID-19: Virus transmission Sickness and / or fatigue Repetitive work, bad posture Health condition of personnel Personal needs and hygiene, fatigue Injuries due to the lack of personal experience. Errors that can compromise the validity of the entire survey Various Injuries, to oneself and other workers Various risks due to usage of alcohol and/or drugs while working on site	5	5	25	5	5	1	5
3	Lack of competence	Injuries due to the lack of personal experience. Errors that can compromise the validity of the entire survey	3	4	12	3	4	1	4
4	Inadequate risk assessment	Various	3	5	15	3	5	1	5
5	Operatives fitness to work	Injuries, to oneself and other workers Various risks due to usage of alcohol and/or drugs while working on site	2	5	10	2	5	1	5
6	Precautionary Measures	Personal injuries if the staff actions do not comply with Health and Safety Best Practices	2	5	10	2	5	1	5
7	Provision of First Aid	Impossibility to treat the injuries	2	5	10	2	5	1	5
8	Provision of Personal Protective Equipment	Various if the Personal Protective Equipment is not within reach or not fit for purpose	2	5	10	2	5	1	5
9	Inadequate risk assessment	Various	2	5	10	2	5	1	5
10	Site access	Injury during the inspection of areas with restricted access due to special / hazardous facilities	5	5	25	5	5	1	5
11	Accessing old buildings or derelict buildings	Injury due to access to not safe areas Slipping - Falling - Tripping	5	4	20	5	4	1	4
12	Accessing in presence of possible harmful substances	Injury and sickness due to contact with harmful substances Asbestos	3	4	12	3	4	1	4
13	Accessing building with not safe electrical system	Touch loose and overhead cables Electrocution, burns death Fatal Shock Tripping Falling	3	5	15	3	5	1	5
14	Accessing the roof of derelict buildings	Falling	5	5	25	5	5	1	5
15	Use of Laser scanner	Eye injury	3	4	12	3	4	1	4
16	Use of drone	High loss of altitude (Loss of control, Loss of transmission, Collision with people, buildings, power lines) Severe weather or climatic events	3	4	12	3	4	1	4
17	Equipment safety	Pilot unfamiliar with area Damage to expensive equipment Assess risk of falling, slipping Expensive repair or replacement costs	3	5	15	3	5	1	5
18	Working in public spaces	Attack/abuse while performing the task on site	3	5	15	3	5	2	5
19	Moving, storing and transporting belongings end equipment	Loss of personal belongings Loss of equipment	3	4	12	3	4	1	4
20	Working near by roads or on the roads	Vehicle hitting equipment or operator Pedestrians tripping over equipment Causing an obstruction	3	5	15	3	5	1	5

Risk Assessment

21	Roads survey	Noise Dust / Fumes Vehicles hitting equipment or operator	Surveyors Contractors	3	5	15	1	5	5
6	Natural risks	Working near or on drainage basins or water (i.e. rivers, artificial channels, sea and stagnant water)	Surveyor Contractor	5	5	25	2	5	10
23	Surveying during adverse weather	Wells Disease Exposure	Surveyor Students	3	4	12	2	4	8
7	Working conditions	Sunburn and Heat-Related Illnesses Slipping - Falling - Tripping Slips, trips, falls	Surveyor Contractor	3	5	15	2	0	0
8	Difficult working conditions	Health hazard Falls Impossibility to be reached by the rescue team Contagious disease Cuts and puncture wounds from sharps	Surveyor Contractor Surveyors Students	4	5	20	2	5	10
25	Confined spaces	Health hazard	Surveyor	4	5	20	2	5	10
26	Working in areas where sharp objects or needles may be present	Health hazard	Surveyor	4	5	20	1	5	5
27	Lifting and handling heavy objects	Falls, trapped toes & fingers, loss of limbs	Surveyor	3	4	12	1	4	4
28	Lifting tripods	Health problems - contracting diseases Damage to back, dropping object on toes	Surveyor	3	4	12	1	4	4
29	Nightwork / Basements	Manual handling Hazards to public	Surveyor	5	5	25	2	5	10
30	Working at heights	Falls	Surveyor	5	5	25	1	5	5
31	rooftop work	Slips, trips, falls	Surveyor Contractor	4	5	20	1	5	5
32	Adverse weather conditions Working at heights / roofs	Working Slips, trips falls	Surveyor Contractor	5	5	25	2	5	10
33	Working on ladders	Slips, trips falls	Surveyor	4	4	16	1	4	4
34	Working directly underneath others	Striking of head Struck by falling objects	Surveyor Contractor	4	5	20	1	5	5
Other						0		0	0

2. Office activity		Hazards - Risks		At Risk		Martix assessment of risk (Max.125)		Control and risk mitigation		Scores after controls put in place (Max.125)	
						Probability		Consequence		Residual Risk	
						1-5		1-5		1-5	
1	Personal risks	Team work, meeting	COVID-19; Virus contagion COVID-19; Virus transmission	Company Client	5	5	25	1	5	5	5
2	Precautions	Inadequate risk assessment	Various	Computer Worker Manager Admin team	5	5	25	1	5	5	5
3	Equipment use	Working with computer workstations. Repetitive motion,	Health risks, posture problems, ache and pain, discomfort or injuries	Computer Worker	5	4	20	1	4	4	4
39		Sore eyes		Computer Worker	5	3	15	1	3	3	3

40	Manual lifting	Noise	Staff	3	4	4	1	4	4
41	Filling shelves, moving equipment	Staff risk injuries or back pain from handling heavy/bulky objects	Staff	3	4	4	1	4	4
42	Falls and trips	Staff risk injuries or back pain from handling heavy/bulky objects	Staff	3	4	4	1	4	4
43	Slips and trips	Staff and visitors may be injured if they trip over objects or slip on spillages.	Staff	3	4	4	1	4	4
44	Stress	Factors such as lack of job control, bullying, workers not knowing their role etc.	Visitor Staff	5	5	5	1	5	5
45	Lone working	Injury or ill health while working alone in the office, out of office, or working from home	Staff	5	5	5	1	5	5
46	Comfort indoor	Verious		5	5	5	1	5	5
5	Electrical hazards	Electrical malfunctions	Staff	3	5	5	1	5	5
6	Fire	Fatal injuries from smoke inhalation, burns, death	Staff	3	5	5	1	5	5
7	Asbestos	Risk if asbestos fibres are released into air and inhaled	Staff	3	5	5	1	5	5
Other									
50				0					1

→ The proposed table shows some of the most common risks that could occur during site and office activities. It contains reference values of probability and gravity of the risks pre and post mitigation action.

Safety risk acceptance

The third step in the Quad2bim safety risk assessment process is to determine the safety risks that require actions.

The safety risk acceptance indicates the combined results of the safety risk probability and safety risk severity assessments. The respective assessment combination is presented in the safety risk assessment matrix shown in the following figures.

Risk Matrix

Probability	5	10	15	20	25
	4	8	12	16	20
	3	6	9	12	15
	2	4	6	8	10
	1	2	3	4	5
	Gravity				

- **The safety risk acceptance level**

-1 to 4 is an acceptable level

-5 to 10 is tolerable

but requires risk mitigation

-11 to 15 is not acceptable

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